

Prevalence of Metabolic Syndrome in Primary Health Care, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

Background: Metabolic Syndrome (MS) is identified as a cluster of risk factors that significantly increase the risk of diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and stroke. It is characterized by obesity, hyperglycemia, dyslipidemia, and hypertension. Multiple definitions and criteria of MS exist. The most widely used set of criteria are the US National Cholesterol Education Program (NCEP) ATP III and the International Diabetes Federation (IDF), both of which are used in this study. Due to different defining criteria and population demographics, the prevalence of MS varies widely across countries, regions, and continents.

Objective: This study investigates the prevalence and risk factors of metabolic syndrome among primary healthcare attendees in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted over 12 months at the Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC) Wazzarat Center in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, involving 262 participants. The study aimed to determine the prevalence and predictors of MS among primary healthcare attendees using ATP III and IDF criteria. Participants were assessed for sociodemographic features, comorbidities, vital signs, and laboratory data related to MS. Statistical analysis utilized R v 4.3 for descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, Chi-square tests for categorical variables, and the Mann-Whitney test for continuous variables.

Results: Among the study participants, 20.2% met the criteria for MS according to ATP III, and 19.9% according to IDF criteria, with a strong concordance between the two (Kappa statistic = 0.92, $P < 0.001$). The median age of individuals with MS was significantly higher (45 years) than those without (35 years, $P < 0.001$). Significant predictors included age, with BMI and fasting blood glucose showing a strong positive correlation ($r > 0.5$, $P < 0.001$). Notably, 60.7% of the cohort were medically free from conditions contributing to MS.

Conclusion: The prevalence of MS among primary healthcare attendees in Riyadh, as defined by ATP III and IDF criteria, underscores the importance of age and lifestyle factors as predictors. The findings advocate for targeted preventive strategies focusing on lifestyle modifications to mitigate the risk of MS. Further research is suggested to explore the long-term impact of these interventions.

Introduction

Metabolic Syndrome (MS) is a co-occurrence of risk factors that are linked with multiple serious health conditions such as diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and stroke. These risk factors include obesity, hyperglycemia, atherogenic dyslipidemia, and

hypertension.[1] In 1988, Dr. Gerald M. 'Jerry' Reaven, an American endocrinologist, named this constellation of symptoms that could predispose to diabetes and cardiovascular disease "Syndrome X". In addition, and for the first time, he introduced the concept of insulin resistance [2]. The following year, it was named the

More Information

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'The Deadly Quartet' by Dr. Norman Kaplan and 3 years later it was renamed as 'The Insulin Resistance Syndrome'[3]. Currently, MS is the term used to describe the cluster of metabolic abnormalities [4]. It was ultimately defined by either the US National Cholesterol Education Program (NCEP) ATP III [5] or International Diabetes Federation (IDF) criteria [6]. The ATP III defines MS as the presence of three or more out of five risk factors including hypertension (blood pressure $\geq 130/85$ mmHg), hyperglycemia (fasting glucose ≥ 100 mg/dL), hypertriglyceridemia (≥ 150 mg/dL [1.695 mmol/L]), low HDL-C (< 40 mg/dL [male] and < 50 mg/dL [female]), and central obesity (waist circumference ≥ 102 cm in males and ≥ 88 cm in females.) The criteria of IDF are similar to ATP III except that central obesity is also essential for the diagnosis. Individuals with MS have a higher likelihood of developing coronary artery disease (CAD), and having MS by itself might anticipate almost one-quarter of new cases of cardiovascular disease [7]. In addition, MS is linked to a higher risk of mortality from coronary heart disease, cardiovascular disease, and all other causes. [8]. It impacts around 25% of the adult population globally, with its occurrence changing according to the definition, ethnicity, and urbanization level [9]. The increase in the prevalence of MS has coincided with the increasing prevalence of type-2 diabetes (T2DM), hypertension, cardiovascular disease, and obesity [10]. The prevalence of metabolic syndrome ranges from 10% to 84% globally in recent research, varying based on factors such as age, sex, and ethnicity of the population [11]. The prevalence of MS is increasing worldwide. In the United States, a study conducted on 17,048 adults between 2011-2016 found MS prevalence of 34.7%. The prevalence significantly correlated with increasing age [12]. Using the ATP III definition of MS, a meta-analysis estimated an average prevalence of 24.3% across European countries [13]. In Greece, a study concluded that 73.6% of primary care attendees over 40 years of age fulfilled the ATP III criteria of MS [20]. A small study conducted in Turkey in 2023 found that 32.97% of primary care attendees had MS [21]. In the African continent, the prevalence of MS was recently found to be 32.4%, with no statistically significant differences between African regions[14]. Moving to Asia, Pakistan has a prevalence of 28.8%, according to a recent systematic review and meta-analysis[15]. In a survey conducted in China from 2015 to 2017, 31.1% of adults were found to fulfill the diagnostic criteria of MS[16]. Furthermore, MS was reported in 37% of Iranian adults according to a cross-sectional study published in 2021[17]. In Member States of the Gulf Cooperative Council (GCC countries), the prevalence ranged from 20.7% to 45.9%. In the meta-analysis, the pooled estimated prevalence was 25% in Oman, 39% in United Arab Emirates (UAE), 28%

in Saudi Arabia, 22% in Kuwait, and 26% in Qatar. Moreover, the prevalence of MS in Saudi Arabia ranged from 11.8% to 40.5%, according to the meta-analysis.[18] A large-scale study that involved 12,126 Saudi adults, and according to ATP III and IDF diagnostic criteria, MS was established in 39.8% and 31.6% of the study subjects, respectively. Also, it was more prevalent among men and older subjects[19]. Several studies around the world were conducted to estimate the prevalence of MS in primary healthcare. A cross-sectional study was conducted among 300 primary healthcare attendees at King Fahad Armed Forces Hospital in Jeddah. The study showed, based on the ATP III criteria, the prevalence of MS was 41.3%. Increasing age, a positive family history of DM, and a history of obesity were the significant risk factors for MS. On the other hand, the prevalence of MS using the IDF criteria was higher (54.3%) and only increasing age and positive family history of DM were significant risk factors for MS20. In Kuwait, 39.4% of 609 Kuwaiti primary care attendees between 30-60 years of age fulfilled the ATP III criteria of MS. And as other studies concluded, the prevalence of MS was significantly associated with increasing age[23]. Another study was done to estimate the prevalence of MS in primary healthcare settings in Qatar on 127,941 Qatari and non-Qatari adults between 18-39 years, the prevalence of MS using ATP III criteria, was 48.8 % [24]. MS has become a global health concern and is a reliable predictor of long-term adverse health outcomes[25]. Unfortunately, people with MS are two times more likely to die and three times more likely to have stroke or heart attack in comparison to people without MS[26]. In addition, people diagnosed with diabetes are at higher risk of developing cardiovascular events. So by early screening and detection of MS, diabetes and/or cardiovascular disease could be prevented[27]. Preventing the development of one MS component is significantly important as the occurrence of one component is predictive of the development of MS[28]. As the global and regional landscapes of metabolic syndrome (MS) prevalence have been outlined, with particular attention to the divergent rates across different populations and criteria, the importance of localized research becomes evident. The variability observed in MS prevalence, influenced by a multitude of factors including demographics, lifestyle, and healthcare access, underscores the necessity for focused studies within specific contexts. This study aims to delve into the prevalence and risk factors of MS among primary healthcare attendees in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. This is essential to enhance healthcare services for primary healthcare attendees by uncovering the prevalence of MS and identifying its associated risk factors within this cohort. Our aim in this study to gain a comprehensive understanding of the prevalence and

risk factors associated with MS among primary health care attendee in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.

Methods

The research was designed as a cross-sectional study aimed at determining the prevalence of metabolic syndrome among attendees of primary healthcare centers in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, and identifying associated risk factors. The study was conducted over a period of 12 months at the Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC) Wazzarat center, a primary healthcare facility that caters to a diverse population in Riyadh. We included all primary healthcare attendees aged 18 or above. People specifically attending the Chronic Illness Clinic or Urgent Care Clinic, and those

below 18 years were excluded. Data was primarily collected from electronic medical records and direct measurements during participants' visits. A structured form was used for data entry. The first part included sociodemographic features such as age, gender, educational level, region of residence, occupation, weight, height, and waist circumference. The second part included comorbidities, vital signs (e.g. blood pressure), and laboratory data for the assessment of MS: lipid profile (TG, LDL, HDL, and total cholesterol), blood glucose, and glycated hemoglobin (HBA1c). Metabolic syndrome was defined based on the criteria set forth by the US National Cholesterol Education Program ATP III and the IDF. (Table 1)

Table 1: ATP III and IDF Criteria of MS

	NCEP ATP III	IDF
Absolutely required	None	Central obesity (waist circumference): ≥ 94 cm (male), ≥ 80 cm (female)
Criteria	Any three of the five criteria below	Obesity, plus two of the four criteria below
Obesity	Waist circumference: >40 inches (male), >35 inches (female)	Central obesity already required.
Hyperglycemia	Fasting glucose ≥100 mg/dL or Rx	Fasting glucose ≥ 100 mg/dL
Dyslipidemia (TG)	TG ≥150 mg/dL or Rx	TG ≥150 mg/dL or Rx
Dyslipidemia (HDL)	HDL cholesterol: <40 mg/dL (male), <50 mg /dL (female); or Rx	HDL cholesterol: <40 mg/dL (male), <50 mg /dL (female); or Rx
Hypertension	>130 mmHg systolic or >85 mmHg diastolic or Rx	>130 mmHg systolic or >85 mmHg diastolic or Rx

In this study, participants were thoroughly informed about the nature of the study and their role within it and, subsequently, written consent was obtained. Confidentiality of participants' information was maintained throughout all phases of the study. Data collected was used exclusively for the purposes of this research. Furthermore, the study protocol was submitted to the Institutional Review Board (IRB) and was granted approval. Statistical analysis was performed using R v 4.3. Counts and percentages were used to summarize categorical variables. The mean ± standard deviation and the median/interquartile range (IQR) were used to summarize continuous normal and non-normal variables, respectively. Chi-square test of independence was used to assess sociodemographic characteristics associated with MS. Both definitions for MS were included in the analysis. The Kappa concordance statistics (K) was used to assess the concordance between the ATP III and IDF definitions for MS [29]. Hypothesis testing was performed at 5% level of significance. The sample size was calculated based on an expected prevalence of metabolic syndrome of 41.3%, with a 95% confidence interval and a 5% margin of error, resulting in a total of 263 participants. Convenience sampling was used in the current study as simple random sampling was not feasible. After

establishing the prevalence rate of MS as a reference for comparison, approximately 263 individuals make up the sample size using the following formula:

$$n = \frac{z_{\alpha/2}^2 \delta^2}{\epsilon^2} \tag{1}$$

$$n = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.413^2}{0.05^2}$$

$$n = 262.10 \approx 263$$

This figure was arrived at by assuming a 95 % confidence interval and margin of error, both with regard to the statistical validity and reliability of our results. A systematic random sampling technique was used.

Results

Descriptive Statistics

As shown in Table 2., the study surveyed a total of 262 respondents. The gender distribution showed a majority of females, accounting for 56.5% (n = 148) of the participants, while males represented 43.5% (n = 114). In terms of smoking habits, the majority of respondents were Non-Smokers, comprising 78.4% (n = 203) of the sample. Comorbidities among the

participants varied, with 17.6% (n = 46) reporting diabetes, 10.7% (n = 28) having Hypertension (HTN), and 9.16% (n = 24) experiencing dyslipidemia.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics for the Study Sample

	[ALL]
	N=262
Age	38.0 [30.0;46.0]
Gender:	
Female	148 (56.5%)
Male	114 (43.5%)
Smoking Habit:	
Ex-smoker (Quit smoking for more than 1 year)	13 (5.02%)
Non-Smoker	203 (78.4%)
Smoker	43 (16.6%)
Comorbidities	
HTN:	28 (10.7%)
Diabetes:	46 (17.6%)
Dyslipidemia:	24 (9.16%)
Hypothyroidism:	7 (2.67%)
Other:	28 (10.7%)
Medically Free:	159 (60.7%)
Prediabetes:	4 (1.53%)
Height (cm)	162 [155;171]
Wt (Kg)	79.0 [66.9;90.7]
BMI (Kg/m²)	29.3 [24.7;34.2]
BMI Category	
Normal	66 (25.2%)
Overweight	74 (28.2%)
Obese	122 (46.6%)
Waist Circumference	98.0 [87.0;110]
Laboratory tests	
TG (mg/dl)	90.3 [68.4;134]
HDL (mg/dl)	48.9 [41.8;58.0]

FBG (mg/dl)	88.2 [81.0;95.0]
Physical activity:	
15-30 min	19 (7.42%)
less than 15 min	28 (10.9%)
more than 30 min	51 (19.9%)
No physical activates	158 (61.7%)
Physical activity (Two categories):	
No PA	158 (61.7%)
PA	98 (38.3%)

Note: Categorical data were summarized using counts and percentages; Continuous data were summarized using the median [IQR]

The median age of participants was 38 years, with an interquartile range (IQR) from 30 to 46 years. Physical measurements indicated a median height of 162 cm (IQR: 155-171 cm) and a weight of 79.0 kg (IQR: 66.9-90.7 kg). The median waist circumference was 98.0 cm (IQR: 87.0-110 cm). Laboratory tests revealed a median Triglyceride (TG) level of 90.3 mg/dl (IQR: 68.4-134 mg/dl), HDL cholesterol level of 48.9 mg/dl (IQR: 41.8-58.0 mg/dl), and Fasting Blood Glucose (FBG) level of 88.2 mg/dl (IQR: 81.0-95.0 mg/dl).

Physical activity levels among respondents varied, with 61.7% (n = 158) reporting no physical activities. Those engaging in physical activities for less than 15 minutes, 15-30 minutes, and more than 30 minutes were 10.9% (n = 28), 7.42% (n = 19), and 19.9% (n = 51), respectively. When categorized broadly, 38.3% (n = 98) engaged in some form of physical activity, whereas 61.7% (n = 158) did not participate in any physical activity.

A statistically significant positive correlation was observed between BMI and WC (r = 0.76, P < 0.001) in both males and females.

Figure 1: Correlation Between Waist Circumference and BMI in Males and Females

Figure 2: Prevalence of MS According to the (A) ATP-III and (B) IDF Criteria

According to the ATP criteria (Figure 2A) for Metabolic Syndrome (MS), 79.8% of the participants did not meet the criteria for MS. However, 20.2% (95% CI 15.81% - 25.51%) of the respondents were found to have MS according to these criteria. When applying the IDF criteria for MS (Figure 2B), the prevalence was similar, with 80.2% of participants not meeting the criteria for MS. According to the IDF standards, the proportion of individuals with MS was 19.9% (95% CI 15.47 – 25.10%). Figure 3 shows that among those not diagnosed with MS by the IDF criteria, 98.1% (n = 206) also did not meet the ATP criteria for MS. In contrast, among individuals diagnosed with MS by the IDF criteria, a significant majority of 94.2% (n = 49) were also diagnosed with MS by the ATP criteria. Only a small fraction, 5.8% (n = 3), were identified as having MS by the IDF criteria but not by the ATP criteria. This suggests a strong concordance between the two criteria in diagnosing MS, with the ATP criteria being slightly more inclusive. The Kappa statistic was 0.92 (P < 0.001), indicating excellent concordance between both methods for classifying MS.

Figure 3: Overlap in Metabolic Syndrome Diagnosis: ATP vs. IDF Criteria

Note: Light Blue: Individuals meeting only ATP criteria for No MS; Dark Blue: Individuals meeting both ATP and IDF criteria for MS

Table 3: Sociodemographic Characteristics and Comorbidities Associated with MS According to the ATP and IDF Criteria

	ATP III			IDF		
	No MS	MS	P	No MS	MS	P
	N=209	N=53		N=210	N=52	
Age	35.0 [29.0;44.0]	45.0 [38.0;53.0]	<0.001	35.0 [29.0;44.8]	45.0 [37.8;51.5]	<0.001
Gender:			1.000			0.725
Female	118 (56.5%)	30 (56.6%)		117 (55.7%)	31 (59.6%)	
Male	91 (43.5%)	23 (43.4%)		93 (44.3%)	21 (40.4%)	
Smoking Habit:			0.505			0.352
Ex-smoker	10 (4.85%)	3 (5.66%)		9 (4.35%)	4 (7.69%)	
Non-Smoker	159 (77.2%)	44 (83.0%)		161 (77.8%)	42 (80.8%)	
Smoker	37 (18.0%)	6 (11.3%)		37 (17.9%)	6 (11.5%)	
Comorbidities						
HTN:	8 (3.83%)	20 (37.7%)	<0.001	8 (3.81%)	20 (38.5%)	<0.001
Diabetes:	14 (6.70%)	32 (60.4%)	<0.001	17 (8.10%)	29 (55.8%)	<0.001
Dyslipidemia:	12 (5.74%)	12 (22.6%)	0.001	11 (5.24%)	13 (25.0%)	<0.001
Hypothyroidism:	4 (1.91%)	3 (5.66%)	0.149	4 (1.90%)	3 (5.77%)	0.143

Other:	25 (12.0%)	3 (5.66%)	0.281	25 (11.9%)	3 (5.77%)	0.302
Medically Free:	149 (71.3%)	10 (18.9%)	<0.001	148 (70.5%)	11 (21.2%)	<0.001
Prediabetes:	1 (0.48%)	3 (5.66%)	0.027	1 (0.48%)	3 (5.77%)	0.026
Height (cm)	163 [156;172]	161 [154;168]	0.182	163 [156;172]	160 [154;168]	0.055
Weight (Kg)	77.0 [64.0;89.0]	85.0 [77.0;100]	<0.001	76.5 [64.1;88.8]	85.8 [77.8;101]	<0.001
BMI (Kg/m2)	28.6 [23.9;32.2]	33.4 [28.1;37.5]	<0.001	28.5 [23.9;32.2]	33.6 [29.8;37.5]	<0.001
WC	94.0 [85.0;107]	110 [102;118]	<0.001	93.0 [85.0;107]	110 [103;118]	<0.001
BMI category:			<0.001			<0.001
Normal	62 (29.7%)	4 (7.55%)		65 (31.0%)	1 (1.92%)	
Obese	84 (40.2%)	38 (71.7%)		82 (39.0%)	40 (76.9%)	
Overweight	63 (30.1%)	11 (20.8%)		63 (30.0%)	11 (21.2%)	
Physical activity:			0.212			0.367
15-30 min	17 (8.33%)	2 (3.85%)		17 (8.29%)	2 (3.92%)	
less than 15 min	24 (11.8%)	4 (7.69%)		23 (11.2%)	5 (9.80%)	
more than 30 min	44 (21.6%)	7 (13.5%)		44 (21.5%)	7 (13.7%)	
No PA	119 (58.3%)	39 (75.0%)		121 (59.0%)	37 (72.5%)	
Physical activity:			0.041			0.106
No PA	119 (58.3%)	39 (75.0%)		121 (59.0%)	37 (72.5%)	
PA	85 (41.7%)	13 (25.0%)		84 (41.0%)	14 (27.5%)	
BMI category						

Note: MS: MS, PA: Physical activity, WC: Waist circumference; Continuous variables were summarized using median [IQR]; Categorical variables were summarized using counts and percentages; Categorical data were compared using the Chi-square test of independence; Continuous variables were compared using the Mann-Whitney test

The median age for individuals without MS was 35 years, but significantly older for those with MS at 45 years (p<0.001) for both criteria sets. Comorbidities like hypertension (HTN), diabetes, and dyslipidemia showed a higher prevalence in the MS group across both criteria, with significant p-values (p<0.001). Regarding physical activity, those without MS engaged more frequently in physical activity than those diagnosed with MS. According to the ATP criteria, the

difference in physical activity levels between the MS and non-MS groups was significant (p=0.041), indicating a potential protective effect of physical activity against MS.

Body mass index (BMI) and waist circumference (WC) were higher among those with MS, with a median BMI of 33.4 Kg/m² and median WC of 110 cm in individuals with M. The median differed significantly from those without MS (p<0.001).

Table 4: Laboratory Results in Individuals with and without MS

	ATP			IDF		
	No MS	MS	P	No MS	MS	P
	N=209	N=53		N=210	N=52	
TG (mg/dl)	84.1 [63.8;107]	168 [129;215]	<0.001	84.1 [64.9;110]	164 [118;209]	<0.001
HDL (mg/dl)	51.0 [44.1;59.6]	40.2 [35.2;46.4]	<0.001	50.5 [44.1;59.5]	41.0 [35.8;48.0]	<0.001
FBG (mg/dl)	84.6 [81.0;93.6]	99.0 [90.0;108]	<0.001	84.6 [81.0;93.6]	98.1 [89.6;108]	<0.001

Note: MS: MS; Continuous variables were summarized using median [IQR]; Continuous variables were compared using the Mann-Whitney test

The analysis of the study data based on the ATP and IDF criteria for metabolic syndrome (MS) revealed significant differences in lipid profiles and blood glucose levels between those diagnosed with MS and those without MS. Under the ATP criteria, individuals without MS had a median TG level of 84.1 mg/dl (IQR: 63.8-107), while those with MS had a much higher median level of 168 mg/dl (IQR: 129-215). HDL

cholesterol presented an inverse relationship, with those without MS showing a median HDL level of 51.0 mg/dl (IQR: 44.1-59.6) compared to a median of 40.2 mg/dl (IQR: 35.2-46.4) for those with MS. Additionally, FBG levels were also significantly different, with a median value of 84.6 mg/dl (IQR: 81.0-93.6) in the non-MS group versus 99.0 mg/dl (IQR: 90.0-108) in the MS group. Similar results were obtained when the IDF

classification was used (Table 4). For all these measures, the differences were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$)

Discussion

MS, is a cluster of risk factors for cardiovascular disease and type 2 diabetes, is influenced by a range of factors. Carnethon identified age, race, education, BMI, alcohol intake, dietary habits, and physical activity as significant risk factors [30]. Grundy emphasized the role of obesity and insulin resistance, exacerbated by physical inactivity, age, and genetic factors [31]. Pedersen added a psychosocial dimension, identifying major life events, lack of social support, and stress reactions as risk factors [32]. These findings underscore the multifactorial nature of metabolic syndrome and the need for a comprehensive approach to its prevention and management. The widespread occurrence of metabolic syndrome is a crucial factor that highlights its significant impact on worldwide public health. Understanding the prevalence of metabolic syndrome in various communities might inform public health approaches and interventions. The prevalence provides healthcare providers and policymakers with crucial information regarding the immediate and extensive resources required to tackle this problem. It also helps identify high-risk groups that could benefit from specific preventive measures and management strategies. Assessing the prevalence of metabolic syndrome is crucial for creating efficient public health policies and therapeutic procedures to decrease its occurrence and lower the risk of related cardiovascular illnesses and type 2 diabetes. In the current study, the prevalence of metabolic syndrome was ~20% which is lower than the prevalence rate observed in other settings in Saudi Arabia. Nonetheless, the prevalence in the current study was similar to that reported in healthy Saudi adults [33]. Indeed, the prevalence on various risk factors in the current study was lower than that reported in other studies with 60.7% being medically free, 10.7% and 17.6% being diagnosed with HTN and diabetes, respectively. The lower prevalence of MS observed in certain studies may be linked to the distinct nature of the patient population served by PSMMC. As a facility primarily catering to military personnel and their families, PSMMC's patient demographic is characteristically different from the general population. Military personnel, due to the nature of their training and duties, are often required to maintain higher levels of physical fitness and adhere to stricter health and fitness regimens than the general populace. This emphasis on physical activity and health maintenance among the military community could contribute to a reduced incidence of metabolic syndrome, as regular exercise and healthy living habits are key factors in preventing the condition. Indeed, these results are similar to those reported by Al Qahtani

who showed that the prevalence of MS in Saudi male soldiers aged 20 years and above was 20.8% [34]. Two representative studies were conducted in Saudi Arabia in 2005 and 2018 which explored the prevalence of MS in the Saudi population. The overall age-adjusted prevalence of MS in the former was 39.3% [35]. In the latter, the prevalence of MS according to the ATP criteria was 38.8% and 31.6% according to the ATP III and IDF criteria, respectively [19]. The slight inconsistency between both studies may be explained by the criteria used for diagnosing MS. Several additional studies have investigated the prevalence and associated factors of MS in various populations within Saudi Arabia with varying results. A study conducted by Balgoon et al. found that that 17.7% of female university students aged 18-25 years at King Abdulaziz University were at risk of developing MS, with increased body mass index (BMI) values associated with an elevated risk similar to what was reported in the current study. The study emphasizes the increasing prevalence of metabolic syndrome among young females due to unhealthy lifestyles [36]. In a research focusing on obese individuals in the Saudi population, Aljabri et al. reported a high prevalence of metabolic syndrome, affecting 69.5% of the studied obese participants. The study highlighted the significant impact of obesity on the risk of developing metabolic syndrome and underscored the need for targeted interventions to manage obesity and related metabolic risks (Aljabri, Bokhari, Alshareef, & Khan, 2018). The high prevalence could be explained by the inclusion criteria where only obese individuals were included in the study. An investigation into the prevalence of metabolic syndrome among former athletes in Saudi Arabia by Altowerqi showed that 52% of the retired athletes had metabolic syndrome, with a considerable percentage exhibiting risk factors such as high waist circumference, high fasting blood glucose, and high blood pressure. This study suggests that even former athletes are not immune to developing metabolic syndrome, highlighting the importance of maintaining a healthy lifestyle post-retirement (Altowerqi, 2020). The variability in the prevalence of metabolic syndrome within Saudi Arabia and across different studies is multifaceted, reflecting the complexity of this health issue. Factors contributing to this variability include population demographics, where studies may focus on different groups characterized by age, gender, and occupation. These demographic variables are critical as they influence metabolic risk factors, with older age groups and specific genders often exhibiting higher prevalence rates [30, 37]. Geographical variation also plays a significant role. Saudi Arabia's diverse geographic landscape encompasses a range of lifestyles, dietary habits, and urbanization levels. The contrast between rural and urban settings can lead to

disparities in physical activity levels and healthcare access, affecting the prevalence of metabolic syndrome. In Saudi Arabia, the prevalence was found to be highest in the Northern and Central regions [38]. Lifestyle factors associated with rapid urbanization and economic development, such as increased sedentary behavior and shifts in diet, particularly the rise in fast food and sugar-sweetened beverage consumption, are significant. These changes contribute to obesity, a central component of metabolic syndrome [39]. Additionally, the interplay of genetic predispositions and environmental factors is notable. Certain genetic factors may predispose the Saudi population to obesity and diabetes, which are magnified by unhealthy lifestyle choices. Variations in socioeconomic status and education levels across study populations can influence lifestyle decisions, health awareness, and healthcare access, further affecting metabolic syndrome prevalence. In addition, the methodology of studies, including sample size and selection techniques, also impacts findings, highlighting the necessity of robust study designs to accurately capture the prevalence of metabolic syndrome. Acknowledging and understanding these contributing factors are essential for crafting effective public health strategies. Tailored interventions that consider these diverse influences and aim to promote healthy lifestyles, improve healthcare access, and target high-risk groups are paramount in addressing the challenges posed by metabolic syndrome effectively.

In the current study, MS was associated with low PA; a finding which was reported in several other studies [36]. These results are also in line with others which showed that a more physically active lifestyle appears to be associated with a lower odds of metabolic syndrome [40]. Physical inactivity and a poor diet have been identified as contributing factors in the development of MS. Approximately 20% of adults worldwide are considered physically inactive [41]. The current study no association between gender and MS. Different studies have shown different results with respect to the association between gender and MS. In a US nationally representative sample of 17,048 individuals, the overall prevalence of MS was 35.1% in males and 34.3% in females indicating that the prevalence on MS was not significantly different among American males and females which is similar to what was reported in the current study [12]. A study conducted in Saudi Arabia, which included more than 17000 participants showed that the prevalence of MS was higher in females although the difference was ~5%. Other studies showed that the prevalence of MS was significantly higher in females than males [42–44]. In contrast, the Saudi-DM study, a representative study of the Saudi population, showed that the prevalence of MS was significantly higher in males than females

[19]. We also observed a statistically significant association between age, body mass index, and the prevalence of MS which was similar to findings from other studies. Research findings indicate that older age, lower education level, less physical activity, and higher BMI are factors that raise the likelihood of developing metabolic syndrome [45]. The rise in metabolic syndrome prevalence with age is mainly due to the high occurrence of metabolic risk factors in those over 65 years old [46].

Concordance between ATP III and IDF criteria for MS

The concordance between the IDF and the ATP III definitions of metabolic syndrome has been explored in various populations to understand which criteria might be more applicable or accurate for diagnosing metabolic syndrome. The IDF places a particular emphasis on central obesity as a prerequisite for diagnosis, along with two or more other metabolic abnormalities, while ATP III criteria require the presence of three or more metabolic abnormalities out of five, without prioritizing any single factor. In the current study, we observed high concordance between the IDF and ATP III definitions for MS. Studies comparing these definitions have found varying levels of agreement and prevalence estimates. A study aiming to evaluate the frequency of metabolic syndrome using the IDF and ATP III definitions in hemodialysis patients found significant variability between the two criteria. This variability suggests that depending on the criteria used, different patients may be classified as having metabolic syndrome, highlighting the need for a unified approach to improve diagnosis and management strategies in clinical practice [47]. Another study assessed the metabolic syndrome prevalence in a French population using the IDF, ATP III, and Hypertriglyceridemic waist criteria. It found that the concordance between the IDF and ATP III definitions was moderate, indicating that while there is some overlap, the two definitions do not always identify the same individuals as having metabolic syndrome. The study also highlighted that the prevalence of metabolic syndrome varied significantly depending on the criteria used, suggesting that the choice of definition can have a substantial impact on the perceived public health burden of metabolic syndrome [48]. These findings underscore the challenges in achieving a consensus on diagnosing metabolic syndrome and the implications for estimating its prevalence and managing affected individuals. The variation in concordance between IDF and ATP III criteria suggests that while both sets of criteria are useful for identifying individuals at increased risk of cardiovascular diseases and diabetes, they may capture slightly different patient populations. This variability underscores the need for clinicians to consider the specific characteristics of their patient populations when choosing which criteria to apply for

diagnosing metabolic syndrome. This study, while providing valuable insights into the prevalence and predictors of Metabolic Syndrome in Riyadh, is not without limitations. Firstly, the cross-sectional design limits the ability to infer causality between the identified risk factors and MS. Additionally, the reliance on convenience sampling may not yield a representative sample of the entire primary healthcare attending population in Riyadh, potentially affecting the generalizability of the findings. The use of self-reported data for lifestyle variables could also introduce bias, as it depends on the participants' recall and honesty. Furthermore, the study's focus on a specific geographic location may limit the applicability of the results to other regions with different socio-economic and cultural backgrounds. Future studies could address these limitations by employing longitudinal designs, random sampling methods, and expanding the study to include diverse populations.

Conclusion

The study reveals a significant prevalence of Metabolic Syndrome (MS) among primary healthcare attendees in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, highlighting the critical role of age and lifestyle in the development of this condition. With approximately 20% of the participants meeting the criteria for MS, the findings underscore the necessity of targeted public health interventions and lifestyle modification strategies to address the risk factors of MS effectively. The strong concordance between the ATP III and IDF criteria further supports the reliability of these diagnostic standards in identifying individuals at risk. This research emphasizes the urgent need for increased awareness and proactive measures to prevent MS, thereby reducing the burden of cardiovascular diseases and diabetes in the population.

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